

Monitoring Past and Future Trends of Urban Heat Island with Geographic Information Systems; Sample of Amasya City

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Abstract

The urban heat island is defined as having higher temperature perceptions in cities than in the surrounding rural areas due to anthropogenic factors. The aim of the study is to monitor the past and future trends of the urban heat island in Amasya with Geographic Information Systems (GIS). Urban heat island was determined according to PET (Physiological Equivalent Temperature) index values using Rayman software. As material, the measurements of Amasya meteorology station and the data of the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios were used. Urban heat island development; calculated from base maps such as altitude, solar radiation, land cover, wind velocity and mean radiant temperature using GIS. The urban heat island in Amasya emerged in the old residential areas of the city and has expanded today. It is foreseen that this expansion trend will continue and intensify in the near and far future. Ecological and sustainable approaches should be developed to reduce the effects of the urban heat island.

Keywords: Urban Heat Island (UHI), Urban climate, Thermal comfort, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Amasya.

Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemleriyle Kentsel Isı Adasının Geçmiş ve Gelecek Eğilimlerinin İzlenmesi; Amasya Kenti Örneği

Öz

Kentlerde antropojenik faktörlere bağlı olarak çevrelerindeki kırsal alanlara göre daha yüksek sıcaklık algılamalarının olması kentsel ısı adası olarak tanımlanmaktadır. Çalışma Amasya'da kentsel ısı adasının Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemleri (CBS) ile geçmiş ve gelecek eğilimlerinin izlenmesini amaçlanmıştır. Kentsel ısı adası, Rayman yazılımı aracılığıyla PET (Physiological Equivalent Temperature) indeksi değerlerine göre belirlenmiştir. Materyal olarak Amasya meteoroloji istasyonunun ölçümleri ile RCP4.5 ve RCP8.5 senaryolarının verileri kullanılmıştır. Kentsel ısı adasının gelişimi; CBS kullanılarak yükselti, solar radyasyon, arazi örtüsü, rüzgâr hızı ve ortalama radyant sıcaklık gibi altlık haritalardan hesaplanmıştır. Amasya'da kentsel ısı adası kentin eski yerleşim alanlarında ortaya çıkmış ve günümüzde genişlemiştir. Bu genişleme eğiliminin yakın ve uzak gelecekte de devam ederek şiddetlenecektir. Kentsel ısı adasının etkilerini azaltmak için ekolojik ve sürdürülebilir yaklaşımlar geliştirilmelidir.

Anahtar kelimeler:Kentsel ısı adası (KSA), Kent iklimi, Termal konfor, Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemleri (CBS), Amasya.

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1. Introduction

Cities are places where education, health, transportation, etc. service sectors develop and industrial activities are intense. In this respect, urban centers have more attractive opportunities than rural areas. With the industrial revolution in the 18th century, cities began to receive intense immigration. Along with technological developments, the development of communication and transportation opportunities and the change in human life philosophy have increased the migration from rural to urban areas. Today, the population of cities is increasing day by day. According to World Bank data, 57% of the world's population is expected to live in cities in 2020, and by 2050, approximately 70% of them are expected to live in cities (Çağlak, Toy & Esringü, 2022).

In Turkey, the majority of the population lives in cities, with the migration from rural to urban areas gaining momentum since 1950. According to 2021 data, the rate of urban population in Turkey has reached 93.2% (province and district centers). This population growth in cities leads to some negative consequences. Reasons such as excessive construction and concretization in urban areas, the increase of impermeable surfaces, the destruction of green areas day by day, the increase in the use of motor vehicles, the development of domestic and industrial heating systems, and the increase in air pollution adversely affect the microclimate characteristics of cities (Demircan & Toy, 2018).

It is included in the studies carried out for Roman cities in B.C., where the cities have different climatic conditions than the rural and semi-rural areas around them and air pollution is high (Yüksel, 2005). The fact that cities have unfavorable climatic conditions such as being hotter and more air pollution than the surrounding rural areas was first defined as an "urban heat island" in Howard's study for the city of London in 1820 (Streutker, 2003; Fan, 2004). Along with the increase in the population of the cities, the urban areas are expanding, the equipment needed by the population is increasing, the traffic and housing density is increasing. The properties of surface materials used in urban areas affect the atmosphere-earth surface energy balance. The scarcity of green areas and water surfaces causes a decrease in heat losses through evapotranspiration in urban areas (Yüksel, 2005). Reasons such as the formation of urban canyons due to dense and high construction, reduced wind speed, insufficient advection and heat transport, pollution and anthropogenic heat pollution cause the formation of an urban heat island (Oke, 1987; Gray & Finster 2005; Nakata & Souza, 2013; Allegrini, Dorer & Carmeliet, 2015; Toy & Esringü, 2021).

The urban heat island effect, which offers adverse climatic conditions, also negatively affects the thermal comfort conditions that directly concern human life and activities. Thermal comfort can be expressed as the state of people feeling comfortable, happy and fit in the thermal environment they are in (Olgay, 1973; Sungur, 1980). Uncomfortable conditions cause many social, economic and physical negativities such as decrease in people's welfare and happiness, health problems and increase in energy use, decrease in work efficiency (Anderson & Bell, 2009; Nastos & Matzarakis, 2012; Fallah & Mayvaneh, 2012; Scherber, Langner & Endlicher, 2014; Çağlak, 2022).

It has been revealed in many studies in the world and in Turkey that cities have negative thermal comfort conditions compared to their surroundings. Clarke & Bach (1971) in Cincinnati, Ohio, USA, Tuller (1980) in Christchurch, New Zealand, Unger (1999) in Szeged, Hungary, Charalampopoulos, Tsiros, Sereli & Matzarakis (2013) in Athens, Greece studies have shown that cities have more negative thermal comfort conditions than rural areas. In studies conducted in Turkey, Çalışkan & Türkoğlu (2014) in Ankara, Çağlak (2017) in Samsun, Tonyaloğlu (2019) in Aydın, Toy, Çağlak & Esringü (2021) in Eskişehir, Çağlak & Türkeş (2022), in Bolu, Çağlak et al, (2022) Erzurum, Metin & Çağlak (2022) in Uşak found that cities are more uncomfortable than rural areas.

In this study, it is aimed to examine the trends of the urban heat island from the past to the future in terms of thermal comfort conditions in the city of Amasya, which is a medium-sized city where industrialization is not developed and located in the Central Black Sea Region of the Black Sea Region of Turkey. In the study, thermal comfort conditions were determined according to the PET index using the Rayman model. ArcGIS 10.5 program from Geographic Information Systems (GIS) software was used in the distribution of the obtained PET values.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Study Area

According to NUTS, the city of Amasya is located in the Samsun sub-region of the Western Black Sea Region (TRA83 Level), between latitudes 40°40'22"N - 40°38'11"N and 35°47'3"E - 35°51'24"E longitudes. Yeşilirmak was decisive in the establishment and development of the city and the city developed between 350-500 meters along the Yeşilirmak valley. There is Çakır Mountain in the northwest of the city and Ferhat Mountain in the southeast (Zeybek, 1998; Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location map of Amasya city

Amasya is in the transition zone between the Black Sea Climate and the Continental Climate. According to Köppen-Geiger climate classification in Amasya; (Csa) climate with mild winter, very hot summer and dry climate; according to Erinç; steppe-semi-arid; according to De martonne; between steppe and humid; according to Thornthwaite; D,B'2,d,b'3 (D: semi-arid, B'2: Mesothermal, d: no excess water or very little, b'3: Summer evaporation rate: 53%) (Bölük, 2016; Çağlak, 2022). According to the long annual measurements of the meteorological station no. 17085 located in the city center, the annual average temperature is 13.6 °C and the annual total precipitation is 460.8 mm. The most precipitation falls in the beginning of winter and spring, the least in summer. The annual average relative humidity was 60% and the annual average wind speed was 1.6 m/s. Average and extreme values are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean and extreme values for Amasya city

Observation Period: 1960 – 2021	Latitude: 40° 39"N	Longitude: 35° 50"E	Elevation: 409 m
Parameters	Value	Date/Period	
Mean temperature (°C)	13.6°C	Annual	
Mean relative humidity (%)	% 60.0	Annual	
Mean wind velocity (m/s)	1.6 m/s	Annual	
Total precipitation (mm)	460.8 mm	Annual	
Mean number of days covered with snow	11.9 days	Annual	
Maximum temperature (°C)	45.0 °C	30.07.2000	
Minimum temperature (°C)	-21.0 °C	15.12.2008	
Highest rainfall in a day	60.9 mm	03.07.1981	
The highest snow thickness	97 cm	05.03.2012	
The fastest wind velocity (m/s)	36 m/s	24.09.1996	

2.2. Method

In the study, the urban heat island was divided into four periods: past (1961 - 1990), present (1991 - 2020), near future (2021 - 2050) and far future (2069 - 2098). For the past (1961 - 1990) and present (1991 - 2020) periods, the Amasya meteorological station, located at an altitude of 405 meters, between 1961 and 2020; air temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), wind (m/s) and cloudiness (octa) measurement data were used. For the near (2021 – 2050) and far future (2069 – 2098) trends, daily (temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and solar radiation) projection data prepared with the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios were used.

The thermal comfort values of the city were determined by the PET index through the Rayman model, which is widely used around the world and includes many parameters in the calculation. PET index is calculated by taking into account all the effects of the thermal environment on humans (short and long wave solar radiation, air temperature, relative humidity and wind speed) and the thermo-physiological conditions of the human body (type of clothing and activity) (Höppe, 1999; Matzarakis, Mayer & Iziomon, 1999; Gulyas, Unger & Matzarakis, 2006). The thermal sensation levels of the PET index were determined by considering a 35-year-old, 175 cm tall, 75 kg, male, healthy individual with 0.9 clo clothing load and 80W workload (Höppe, 1999; Matzarakis et al., 1999; Table 2).

Table 2. Human thermal sensation and stress ranges for PET (Matzarakis et al., 1999; Gulyas et al., 2006)

PET (°C)	Thermal Sensation	Level of Thermal Stress
<4.0	Very Cold	Extreme cold stress
4.1–8.0	Cold	Strong cold stress
8.1–13.0	Cool	Moderate cold stress
13.1–18.0	Slightly Cool	Slight cold stress
18.1–23.0	Neutral (Comfortable)	No thermal stress
23.1–29.0	Slightly Warm	Slight warm stress
29.1–35.0	Warm	Moderate heat stress
35.1–41.0	Hot	Strong heat stress
>41.0	Very Hot	Extreme heat stress

ArcGIS 10.5 program, one of the Geographical Information Systems software, was used in the spatial distribution of the PET values obtained for the determination of the urban heat island. First of all, the elevation map of the city was prepared in the form of a digital elevation model (DEM), then using the DEM base, an area solar radiation map was produced with the "Area Solar Radiation" tool of the ArcGIS 10.5 program. Then, a land cover map was prepared and the distribution of wind speed was obtained according to this map. Using the land cover, altitude and solar radiation values, mean radiant temperature map was obtained via MrT software (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Basemaps used

After these base maps were obtained as raster, the determined PET value was distributed over the entire surface with the same value. Then, with the "Raster Calculator" tool of ArcGIS 10.5 program, the distribution of PET values was obtained by considering the effect levels of base maps on PET values. Urban heat islands were determined by mapping the obtained distributions.

3. Findings and Discussion

In the past, PET values in Amasya were found to range between 9.8 °C and 14.6 °C. The urban heat island effect was evident in Hacı İlyas Neighborhood, which is an old residential area. It is also evident as a heat plateau in Şamlar, Kurşunlu, Beyazıtpaşa, Yüzevler and Ellibeşevler neighborhoods (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The urban heat island of Amasya in the past (1961 – 1990)

Today, PET values vary between 12.1 C and 16.8 °C. Compared to the past, PET values increased by 2.2 °C. The number of urban heat islands has increased and their area has expanded. Urban heat islands have emerged in Hacilyas, Şamlar, İhsaniye and Ellibeşevler neighborhoods. The heat plateau is seen in Kurşunlu, Beyazıtpaşa, Pirinççi, Mehmetpaşa, Savadiye, Yüzevler and Şehirüstü neighborhoods. The heat plateau has expanded even more than in the past. In addition, heat plateau formations have started in Şeyhcui and Akbilek neighborhoods, which are known as new settlement areas (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Today's (1991 – 2020) urban heat island of Amasya

In the near future, PET values in Amasya are predicted to vary between 13.8 °C and 18.6 °C according to the RCP4.5 scenario, and between 14.6 °C and 19.4 °C according to the RCP8.5 scenario. PET values are expected to increase between 1.8 °C and 2.5 °C from today. It is noteworthy that the urban heat island will expand further according to both scenarios. In particular, according to the RCP8.5 scenario, the urban heat island is predicted to extend from the Hacılıyas District to the Ellibeşevler District in the south of the city. A large urban heat island is also expected in the districts of Şamlar, İhsaniye and Bahçeleriçi, which are located in the northeast of the Yeşilirmak River. It is predicted that the heat plateau will develop in Şeyhcuı and Akbilek districts, which are the new residential areas and are the favorite places of the city (Figure 5; Figure 6).

Figure 5. The trend of urban heat island in the city of Amasya in the near future (2021 – 2050) according to the RCP4.5 scenario

Figure 6. The trend of urban heat island in the city of Amasya in the near future (2021 – 2050) according to the RCP8.5 scenario

In the distant future (2069 – 2098), PET values are expected to vary between 16.1 °C and 20.7 °C in the RCP4.5 scenario and between 16.8 °C and 21.7 °C in the RCP8.5 scenario in the city of Amasya. It is predicted that PET values will increase between 4 °C and 5 °C compared to today. According to the RCP4.5 scenario, the urban heat island effect will intensify, and it will affect a large part of Mehmetpaşa Neighborhood, from the northeast of the Bıçakçı District, which joins the south of Ellibeşevler District and the southwest of Kirazlıdere District and includes Beyazıtpaşa District. An urban heat island is expected to cover the Hacılıyas, Yüzevler, Şehirüstü neighborhoods and the north of the Dere District. Urban heat island formation is also expected in Kurşunlu District. There is a tendency to form an expanding urban heat island in the districts of Şamlar, İhsaniye and Bahçeleriçi in the northwest of the city (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The trend of urban heat island in the city of Amasya in the distant future (2069 - 2098) according to the RCP4.5 scenario

According to the RCP8.5 scenario, very severe urban heat island formations are predicted to occur in the distant future. An urban heat island is expected to start from the east of the Hacılar Meydan quarter in the south of the Yeşilirmak River and will be effective in all of the Hacılıyas, Yüzevler, Şehirüstü, Dere, Sofular, Gümüşlü, Mehmetpaşa, Savadiye, Pirinççi, Beyazıtpaşa neighborhoods and most of the Kirazlıdere and Ellibeşevler neighborhoods. It is predicted that the urban heat island, which expands in the districts of Şamlar, İhsaniye and Bahçeleriçi in the northwest of the city, will extend to the banks of the Yeşilirmak River. Another urban heat island formation is expected in the area extending from Kurşunlu Mahallesi to the west of Hızırpaşa Mahallesi and Şeyhcu neighbourhood (Figure 8).

conditions of cities and create an urban heat island. This situation has been demonstrated concretely in many cities in the world and in Turkey.

It is extremely important to present the urban heat island formations in a concrete way and to follow the trends of the urban heat islands in terms of socio-economic planning and spatial designs. Knowing the size and changes of urban heat islands is extremely important for every professional discipline that is related to the results of such developments. These results serve as a guide for the development of consistent policies going forward.

It is necessary to reduce the urban heat islands that cause adverse conditions and to work towards climate resistant sustainable cities. Cool environments such as parks, green roofs and water surfaces should be created in urban areas and distributed evenly throughout the city. For sustainable healthy cities, it is necessary to make urban design and planning from a geographical perspective (taking into account human, biotic and physical environmental conditions).

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The article complies with national and international research and publication ethics. Ethics Committee approval was not required for the study

Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Disclosure Information

The article has a single author. There is no conflict of interest.

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